

1 Review on technology climate impact assessment
2 methodologies and resulting best practice

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44 **Abstract**

45 The climate impact of aviation resulting from both CO₂ emissions and non-CO₂
46 effects is gaining attention from aviation stakeholders seeking to identify potential
47 mitigation options. There is a need to consolidate the use of assessment meth-
48 ods and climate metrics, which are required to convert aviation non-CO₂ effects
49 into CO₂-equivalent emissions. We provide an overview of the operational, tech-
50 nological and scenario-based climate impact assessment methods that have been
51 applied in literature as well as considerations and requirements for the choice
52 of climate metric. We propose a four-layer technology climate impact assess-
53 ment methodology, which includes: (1) the technology parameters, such as entry
54 into service and temporal and spatial network use; (2) the calculation of three-
55 dimensional aircraft trajectories and emission inventories; (3) the calculation of
56 radiative forcing and induced temperature change time series; and (4) the over-
57 all climate impact, measured using a climate metric. We recommend two climate
58 metrics that best fulfill the requirements, the Average Temperature Response
59 (ATR100) and the Efficacy-weighted Global Warming Potential (EGWP100),
60 both over 100 years. Additionally, we discuss further steps, such as the under-
61 standing of the most sensitive parameters in this approach, how uncertainties
62 can be included to provide robust estimates, aspects of verification and update
63 possibilities for new findings in research.

64 **Keywords:** Aviation climate impact, Aviation emissions, Climate impact technology
65 assessment, Climate metrics, Contrails, Nitrogen oxides

66 **1 Introduction**

67 The climate impact of aviation stems from both CO₂ emissions and non-CO₂ emis-
68 sions and effects. The latter comprise the emission of NO_x, H₂O, particulates and the

69 formation of persistent contrails [1]. These emissions and effects alter the atmospheric
70 abundance of species and the cloudiness, leading to changes in the Earth’s radiation
71 budget, which is widely described using the concept of Radiative Forcing (RF). As
72 a consequence, the climate is changing, affecting near-surface temperatures as well
73 as other atmospheric parameters such as precipitation patterns and extreme weather
74 events. Among these, the near-surface temperature change is a frequently used and
75 a well-accepted indicator of climate change [2, 3] which is addressed by the Paris
76 Agreement [4].

77 While the assessment of the climate impact of the aviation sector is based on a
78 well-established method, including the choice of a climate metric, this is not the case
79 for the climate impact assessment of individual future aviation technologies. Aviation
80 climate impact assessments [1, 5–7] mostly apply a backward-looking approach, using
81 RF and Effective Radiative Forcing (ERF) to analyse the impact of aviation emis-
82 sions from roughly 1940 to ”present” (at the time of the respective publication). ERF
83 is calculated once fast atmospheric adjustments, e.g. cloud changes, continental tem-
84 perature changes are accounted for. A few studies also refer to temperature changes,
85 which additionally use the concept of efficacy to include slow feedback processes such
86 as changes in ocean temperatures [e.g. 2, 3, 8].

87 The main differences of these aviation climate impact assessments compared to
88 technology climate impact assessments stem from the following factors: (1) compared
89 to possible future technology scenarios, historical evolution of aviation emissions is
90 well constrained due to availability of data and long-term records; (2) the focus is
91 on the effects of past, accumulated impacts on the present day (backward-looking
92 approach), rather than on impacts from upcoming technologies on the climate at a
93 later point in time; (3) the background conditions, e.g. impact from other sectors, are
94 well constrained, whereas for future conditions different scenarios exist.

95 In Section 2, we provide an overview of climate impact assessments of aviation
96 mitigation options. Section 3 then presents and discusses requirements for the choice
97 of climate metrics for aviation. Based on this broad, though certainly not exclusive
98 overview, we derive a best practice for a technology climate impact assessment work-
99 flow (Sec. 4.1), present examples of its application (Sec. 4.2), and discuss knowledge
100 gaps in both the sensitivities in the workflow and the uncertainties in the assessment
101 itself (Sec. 5).

102 This work was performed within the CLAIM project (Clean Aviation Support
103 for Impact Monitoring, <https://www.claim-project.eu/>) funded by European Union,
104 where a best practice for a climate impact assessment was developed and presented in
105 two workshops to stakeholders from industry, academia and policy. The detailed and
106 fruitful feedback is incorporated here in the recommended methodology (Sect. 4).

107 2 Climate impact assessments

108 In this section, we provide an overview of the literature and projects that described
109 and performed climate impact assessments. We focus on the methods that have been
110 applied rather than the findings. The main characteristics of these methods are sum-
111 marised in Table 1. We discriminate between three main areas: operational mitigation

Table 1 Overview on characteristics of climate impact assessments applied in literature. The temporal evolution of emissions are abbreviated with P, S, L, F, H for pulse, sustained, lifetime, future and historic evolution; ISO, MF-BWB and LCA stand for intermediate-stop-operations, multi-fuel blended wing body and life-cycle assessment, respectively.

Project / Institution	Spatial emission	Temporal emis.	Climate metric	Time horizon H [yr]	Topic	Reference
Operational						
REACT4C, ATM4E, FlyATM4E	4D trajectory data	F-ATR, S-ATR, S-AGTP, P-GWP		20, 100	Climate-optimised routing	[9]
Imperial College / DLR	4D trajectory data	P	GWP (EF)	100	Contrail-optimised routing	[10]
DLR / ClimOP	3D inventories	F	ATR	20, 100	ISO	[11, 12]
FormIC	3D inventories	F	ATR	50, 100	Formation flight	[13]
TRADEOFF	3D inventories	Var. F	RF, AGTP	100	Cruise altitude changes	[14]
REACT4C	3D inventories	H	RF, AGTP	66	Cruise altitude changes	[15]
Technological						
CRYO-PLANE	mission	P	GWP	100	H ₂ -aircraft	[16]
Stanford	mission + response from 3D inventory	L	ATR _r ¹	500	Aircraft design	[17]
GLOWOPT/TU Delft	as above	L	GTP	100	Aircraft design	[18]
TUM, AIR-BUS	as above	S	GTP	100	Aircraft design	[19]
MTU	as above	S	GTP	100	Aircraft design	[20]
CATS	3D inventory	L	ATR	100	Aircraft design	[21, 22]
AHEAD	3D inventory	F	ATR	100	MF-BWB	[23]
WeCare/FrEACs	3D inventory	F	ATR	100	Strut-braced wing aircraft	[24]
EXACT	3D inventory	L	ATR	100	synthetic kerosine & green hydrogen powered mid-range aircraft	[25]
EXACT	3D inventory	P	GWP, ATR	100	LCA of LH ₂ -aircraft design	[26]
MINIMAL	3D inventory	F	ATR	100	Engine climate optimisation	[27]
Scenario						
ETH	global means	F	GWP*	100	Pathways to climate neutrality	[28]
IMPACT	global means	F	RF, dT	n.a.	Future aviation CO ₂ impacts	[2]
ECATS	3D inventories	F	RF, dT	n.a.	Aviation, Paris Agreement	[3]

¹This version of ATR includes a discount rate r after the aircraft is taken out of service. Note that for $r = 0$ the definition is identical to ATR used in other studies.

112 options (Sec. 2.1), technological mitigation options (Sec. 2.2), and analysis of var-
113 ious scenarios, i.e. projections for future air traffic (Sec. 2.3). We summarise the
114 methodological approaches in Sec. 2.4.

115 2.1 Operational climate mitigation options

116 The avoidance of climate sensitive regions (e.g. contrail avoidance) is one of the
117 most promising operational climate mitigation options. The modelling concept for the
118 approach in the EU projects REACT4C [29], ATM4E [30] and FlyATM4E [31] is
119 presented in Grewe et al. [9]. They calculated the impact of a local emission, assum-
120 ing specific weather situations, resulting in 4D datasets (three spatial coordinates
121 and time), so-called climate change functions (CCF) that describe expected climate
122 impacts per aviation emission or flown distance for CO₂, NO_x, H₂O emissions and
123 contrails. By multiplying the datasets with 4D emissions of planned flights, trade-
124 off between CO₂ and non-CO₂ climate effects for climate optimized routing could be
125 analyzed. They considered a pulse emission and several pathways of projected future
126 emissions (emission scenarios). In their Table 7, they summarised the research ques-
127 tion as "What is the short/long-term climate impact of the REACT4C re-routing
128 strategy?" and concluded to focus "on the metrics F-ATR20, F-ATR100, P-GWP20
129 and P-GWP100 in future applications". Here F and P denote future scenarios and
130 pulse emissions, respectively, and 20 and 100 denote the time horizons in years.

131 Teoh et al. [10] investigated trade-offs in climate effects resulting from contrail
132 avoidance in the Japanese air space. They concentrate on pulse emissions and calculate
133 the Energy Forcing (EF), which is essentially equivalent to GWP100 with other units
134 (see supplement of Irvine et al. [32] and Borella et al. [33]). GWP100 is also used
135 directly for the CO₂ climate impact and then recalculated into EF. Hence, we regard
136 GWP100 as the basic underlying metric in this study. Similar approaches were used
137 in Quante et al. [34], Borella et al. [33] and others.

138 Besides those operational measures that take advantage of the day-by-day variation
139 in the weather system and the large variability in aviation climate effects, additional
140 strategic operational measures were examined. Linke et al. [11] and Zengerling et al.
141 [12] analysed the climate impact mitigation potential for intermediate stop operations
142 (ISO), which refers to one or more stops at airports between the origin and final
143 destination of an aircraft allowing it to transport less fuel over a long distance and
144 thus to reduce the amount of fuel burnt over the mission. They used 3D inventories
145 of aviation emissions that either include or exclude ISO. The studies adopted an
146 increasing emission evolution together with the ATR20 and ATR100.

147 Similar to this approach, the potential for reducing the climate impact through the
148 use of aerodynamic formation flight was analysed in Dahlmann et al. [13]. They also
149 employ ATR100 to quantify the climate impact. Emission inventories were calculated
150 for the most popular airport pairs assuming that the emissions increase according to
151 the future Fa1 scenario as defined in IPCC [35].

152 Frömming et al. [14] investigated general flight altitude changes that are imple-
153 mented from the year 2000 and follow a future aviation scenario with various variations
154 (lasting for 15 years, constant after 2050, following the future scenario). The avia-
155 tion emissions are based on detailed 3D-inventories for the year 2000. The RF and

156 the temperature change 100 years after the start of the implementation (i.e. 2100) of
157 this strategy is used as a climate metric (RF100, AGTP100). Here and throughout
158 the paper, "A" in front of the metric denotes an absolute climate metric (e.g. AGTP,
159 AGWP, AEGWP). Similarly, Matthes et al. [15], investigated general cruise altitude
160 changes with an updated 3D-emission inventory and using annual historic emissions
161 form 1940 to 2006 (66 years) to analyse RF and temperature changes (AGTP) for the
162 year 2006.

163 2.2 Technological climate mitigation options

164 Svensson et al. [16] investigated lower flying liquid hydrogen-driven (LH₂) aircraft
165 in comparison to a kerosene-driven aircraft. They combined atmospheric modeling
166 results to provide an altitude-dependent GWP response function for NO_x- and H₂O-
167 emissions. Schwartz-Dallara and Kroo [17] applied an optimisation approach to derive
168 aircraft designs that minimise their climate impact. They used a typical mission,
169 i.e. a typical aircraft trajectory and emissions along that trajectory and combined it
170 with pre-calculated atmospheric responses (RF) of aviation emission for NO_x-, H₂O-
171 emissions and contrails that were obtained by using a 3D-inventory [36, 37]. They
172 considered a 30-year service life of the aircraft (lifetime emission, L) and analysed
173 the averaged temperature response over 500 years, where the temperature change
174 after the aircraft use is weighted by a discount rate r (ATR_r). Egelhofer [19] used
175 the same methodology, though concentrated on sustained emissions and the global
176 temperature potential over 100 years (S-GTP100). Similar approaches were used by
177 Proesmans and Vos [18] who relied on a linearisation of the same response functions
178 [17], but used a slightly changed temporal evolution of the emissions with a ramp-up
179 phase, a maximum use of 5 years and a phase-out that leads to 65 years of emissions.
180 Pouzolz et al. [20] applied the same atmospheric response functions for the climate
181 optimisation of aircraft design and an aircraft propelled by a water-enhanced turbofan
182 engine, respectively. However, they used a pulse emission and GWP as the underlying
183 climate metric.

184 Koch et al. [21] and Dahlmann et al. [22] investigated the relation between changes
185 in climate impact and operational costs when changing cruise speed and altitude. They
186 optimised an aircraft for an eco-efficient setting of altitude and speed. The climate
187 impact assessment uses 3D inventories for each of the regarded settings of cruise speed
188 and altitude and assumes a lifespan of 32 years where emissions take place (L) and
189 applied the climate metric ATR100. Grewe et al. [23] investigated the climate impact
190 of a multi-fuel blended wing body. The engine features two combustion chambers: the
191 first burns hydrogen, the second sustainable aviation fuel using flameless technology. A
192 3D inventory was calculated for this aircraft. The temporal evolution of the emissions
193 is characterised by an entry into service in 2050 with a constant increase of the fleet
194 size until 2075. After 2075 the overall aviation emissions are increasing (F) and the
195 market share of the AHEAD aircraft remains constant. A comparable approach was
196 used in Grewe et al. [24] for the assessment of a strut-braced wing. Both studies based
197 the climate impact evaluation on ATR100. While the above studies assessed emissions
198 during flight, only, Ramm et al. [26] investigated the whole life cycle and base their
199 estimates on a pulse emission combined with GWP100. For the emissions they based

200 their assessment on a 3D European emission inventory, while Silberhorn et al. [25]
201 investigated the impact of synthetic kerosene and green hydrogen powered mid-range
202 aircraft using ATR100 for a lifetime emission.

203 **2.3 Scenario assessments**

204 For completeness, several scenario assessments are included in Table 1 to provide a
205 more comprehensive understanding of assessment strategies. All those studies have
206 in common that future temporal changes in aviation emissions and their impacts are
207 the main objectives, whereas operational and technological assessments utilize the
208 temporal evolution of emissions as merely a means for calculating the impact of a
209 mitigation option. Therefore, the temporal evolution of the emissions is marked with
210 an F (Table 1).

211 Climate metrics are then often used to convert the impact of non-CO₂ effects
212 into equivalent CO₂ emissions. For this conversion, Brazzola et al. [28], e.g. used the
213 climate metric GWP* [38] that includes a time horizon and refers to the changes in the
214 emission scenario. Note that the star-metrics are generally evaluated to be suitable for
215 scenario calculations, but unsuitable as an emission metric [39, 40] or for technology
216 assessments [41, see also Sec. 3]. Terrenoire et al. [2] concentrated on the impact
217 of future CO₂ emissions and hence a detailed 3D inventory is not necessary, as the
218 location of the emission is not relevant for its impact in this case. They investigated the
219 temporal evolution of the associated RF and temperature changes with the OSCAR
220 model and discussed changes for 2050 and 2100 in more detail, without the necessity
221 to apply climate metrics, although the discussion of the temperature change in the
222 year 2100 can also be interpreted as AGTP(2100). Similarly, Grewe et al. [3] analysed
223 top-down and bottom-up emission scenarios and tested the alignment with the Paris
224 Agreement. Since also non-CO₂ effects were included, detailed 3D emission inventories
225 were calculated and the discussion concentrates on temperature changes, and identified
226 time horizons where a temperature change is surpassing a certain limit.

227 **2.4 Summary on assessment characteristics**

228 The overviews of both operational and technological mitigation options, discussed in
229 Sec. 2.1 and 2.2, share a common feature: they both incorporate a detailed 3D emis-
230 sion analysis that takes into account the location of the emissions. Figure 1 presents an
231 overview of climate indicators and respective time horizon values adopted in the oper-
232 ational (blue), technological (red) and scenario (orange) assessments listed in Table 1.
233 It shows that that for technology climate impact assessments, ATR was frequently
234 combined with life-cycle (L) or future increasing emissions (F) to describe the tem-
235 poral evolution of the technology's emissions and AGWP and AGTP were combined
236 with pulse (P) and sustained (S) emissions. On the other hand, the selection of the
237 climate metrics in operational climate impact assessments varies much more. This
238 might be seen as obvious, since a technology option requires a much longer time for
239 implementation and hence short-term climate metrics are seen as inappropriate.

Fig. 1 Overview on the used climate metrics in climate impact assessment studies (see Tab. 1). The temporal evolution of emissions are abbreviated with letters P, S, L, F, H for pulse, sustained, lifetime, future and historic aviation evolution, respectively. The colors blue, red and orange represent operational, technological and scenario measures, respectively. For visibility reason, the symbols are slightly displaced. The red shaded area indicated climate metric combination used for technology climate impact assessments.

240 3 Choices for climate metrics in technology climate 241 impact assessments

242 3.1 Introduction

243 A climate metric enables the conversion of non-CO₂ emissions and effects into CO₂
244 equivalents, providing a common scale for processes with varying timescales for mit-
245 igation strategy development. There is no consensus in the science community on
246 the most suitable climate metric for aviation [e.g. 42]. The GWP for pulse or sus-
247 tained emissions has been traditionally used in policy-making [43], for example, in
248 single-basket schemes such as the European Emission Trading System (ETS) and in
249 the recently established aviation non-CO₂ Measurement, Reporting, and Verification
250 (MRV) framework. An advantage of the GWP for a pulse emission is that it can be
251 calculated with a simple analytical approach, for which data are readily available.
252 However, the GWP has been criticised over years, especially when considering avia-
253 tion effects that do not depend on emissions alone [42, 44] and due to its sensitivity
254 to the time horizon [e.g. 45]. Moreover, this metric does not fully capture the com-
255 plex interactions and feedback mechanisms in the climate system that influence actual
256 temperature changes and climate impacts [42, 46]. Many alternative physical metrics

257 have been proposed in literature such as the end-point metrics RF and GTP, efficacy-
258 weighted GWP (EGWP), integrated GTP (iGTP), and ATR. Furthermore, flow-based
259 metrics GWP* and EGWP* metrics have been introduced recently to include the
260 effect of short-lived climate pollutants.

261 The choice of a climate metric that includes an emission evolution (pulse, sus-
262 tained, etc.), the time horizon and the climate indicator (AGWP, ATR, etc.) strongly
263 influence the outcome of the impact evaluation and potentially affect decision making.
264 Because of the different timescales of the CO₂ and non-CO₂ effects, the time horizon
265 value affects the perceived importance of different emissions [42, 47]. Additionally, the
266 temporal emission evolution weights short-lived effects more when considering scenar-
267 ios rising over time, compared to declining scenarios or pulse emissions [48]. Hence,
268 different metrics can yield values with varying signs, highlighting the importance of
269 selecting the most appropriate metric for policy decisions [42]. Analysis of poten-
270 tial contrail avoidance strategies indicates that climate benefit from flight rerouting
271 depends on both the time horizon and metric definition [33]. Applying new metrics
272 like GWP* within existing climate policy contexts should be approached with caution,
273 as their use in interpreting the Paris Agreement goals can lead to inconsistencies
274 in the mitigation framework and potentially undermine the net-zero CO₂ emissions
275 target [49].

276 Selecting an appropriate climate metric thus involves decisions regarding the phys-
277 ical indicator represented by the metric (e.g. radiative forcing or temperature), the
278 choice between end-point and integrated metrics, the adopted time horizon and the
279 underlying emission scenario. For aviation emissions, a further challenge with the
280 choice of a metric is that the emission effects vary with altitude, location, and emission
281 time. A method that accounts for this dependence as well as changes in the background
282 relies on simple climate response models which we will discuss in Sect. 4.3.

283 In summary, the multiplicity of climate metrics for aviation imposes a perceived
284 ambiguity that potentially leads to a hurdle in the acceptance of a climate impact
285 technology assessment. Grewe and Dahlmann [50] stress that not all climate metrics
286 are equally suited for addressing a specific research question, and the careful framing
287 of such questions can significantly reduce this perceived ambiguity. Megill et al. [41]
288 further narrowed down the climate metric selection process by defining requirements
289 that are for the most part taken from literature and testing climate metrics against
290 those requirements by contrasting a scenario analysis and the climate metrics values
291 for 10,000 potential aircraft fleets. In the following, we summarise and discuss these
292 results as a basis for a recommendation and best practice given in Sec. 4.

293 **3.2 Requirements for climate metric evaluation**

294 To evaluate the applicability of existing physical metrics to the aviation industry,
295 Megill et al. [41] formulated main requirements for physical climate metrics based on
296 the primary needs of aviation, including trajectory optimisation, aircraft design, and
297 policy development. Performance of both traditional and new climate metrics was then
298 evaluated against these requirements. The proposed set of requirements stipulates that
299 a climate metric must be

- 300 • **neutral**, which includes two aspects: first, that a climate metric neutrally represents
301 results from a respective scenario assessment and second, that there is no bias
302 towards a specific technology;
- 303 • **temporally stable**, which refers to its ability to represent climate impacts con-
304 sistent over different periods of time and be insensitive to small variations of the
305 time horizon;
- 306 • **compatible** with existing climate policy;
- 307 • **simple to understand and implement** for non-specialists (requirement of the
308 climate metric transparency).

309 Below, we briefly discuss each requirement and summarise the outcome of evaluation of
310 physical metrics (see Table 2 in Megill et al. [41] for definitions of the metrics) against
311 these requirements. Note that the integrated GTP (iGTP) and the ATR metric are
312 in principle the same, differing only by a factor of H and expressed in units of mK yr
313 and mK, respectively.

314 *Climate metric neutrality*

315 The first requirement implies that a climate metric should neutrally represent the cho-
316 sen climate indicator, which describes the climate change caused by the considered
317 technology. In practice, it means that the climate metric should be unbiased towards
318 any specific aircraft concept changes. The peak temperature was selected as an indica-
319 tor of climate change for evaluation of metric neutrality (see Sect. 3.4 for a discussion
320 of this choice). A metric correctly represents the temperature change when the differ-
321 ence in the climate impacts of two technological options 1 and 2 evaluated with this
322 climate metric (CM) has the same sign as the difference in their temperature changes
323 (ΔT)

$$(CM_1 - CM_2) \times (\Delta T_1 - \Delta T_2) > 0. \quad (1)$$

324 In order to test the neutrality of climate metrics, Megill et al. [41] perform fleet pairing
325 analysis on a large set of future aircraft fleets. Each fleet is generated with the Monte
326 Carlo method by varying the fuel type, CO₂ and non-CO₂ emissions and effects, flight
327 altitude, year of fleet introduction, and background concentration. The response model
328 AirClim is used for the climate impact assessment [51, 52].

329 Figure 2 shows the differences in the peak temperature changes for randomly
330 selected fleet pairs vs. the corresponding differences in the climate metric values for
331 the selected climate metrics. The fleet pairs in the red quadrants in Fig. 2 are incor-
332 rect fleet pairs that do not satisfy the condition given by Eq. (1). Generally, climate
333 metrics with the lowest scatter of fleet pairs such as ATR, AEGWP, EGWP* are
334 representative of the temperature changes and have high neutrality and vice versa.

335 *Temporal stability*

336 The requirement of temporal stability ensures that the impact assessment with a
337 climate metric remains accurate and consistent over different time periods. This
338 requirement is particularly relevant for monitoring purposes in aviation policy. The
339 stability of climate metrics was assessed by analysing the temporal developments
340 of CO₂-eq emission in two future aviation emission scenarios, CORSIA and Flight-
341 Path2050 [3]. The analysis shows a poor performance of the GWP* and EGWP*

Fig. 2 The peak temperature change $\Delta T_1 - \Delta T_2$ vs. the difference in the climate metric $CM_1 - CM_2$ for randomly selected fleet pairs. The lower right panel shows the areas enclosing the incorrect fleet pairs (red quadrants), which do not fulfill the condition given by Eq. 1. The proportion of fleet pairs within these areas determines the neutrality of a metric. Adopted from the supplement of Megill et al. [41].

342 metrics against this requirement, whereas the rest of the metrics show relatively similar
 343 trends.

344 *Compatibility with climate policy*

345 The compatibility of a climate metric with existing climate policy requires that the
 346 metric aligns with policy goals and is easily integrated into existing reporting and
 347 monitoring systems used by governments, organisations, and industries. We evaluate
 348 compatibility of a climate metric with climate policy in terms of its functionality: it is
 349 considered compatible if it provides similar functionality as the most commonly used
 350 GWP. In the context of the aviation industry, this implies that a metric should allow
 351 to calculate (1) the temporal evolution of CO₂-eq emissions and (2) a single value for
 352 a given time horizon for fleets and individual flights for application in the ETS. All
 353 conventional climate metrics – RF, GWP, GTP, iGTP and ATR – can provide this
 354 functionality and hence can be used in existing climate policy. Temperature-based
 355 metrics are however considered more policy-relevant due to their link to temperature
 356 change targets. The GWP* and EGWP* metrics have difficulties with the condition
 357 (2). The GWP* method is designed to provide a continuous assessment that reflects
 358 ongoing changes in emissions and their immediate impacts. The GWP* and EGWP*
 359 metrics effectively have a second time horizon that corresponds to the time span during
 360 which change in the emission rate is considered.

361 Schlessner et al. [49] find that applying GWP* directly to interpret the goals of
 362 the Paris Agreement can lead to profound inconsistencies in its mitigation architecture.
 363 The Paris Agreement focuses on the evolution of annual emission rates over time,

Table 2 Performance evaluation of climate metrics against respective requirements. Performance is ranked from $---$ (very low) to $+++$ (very high).

Metric	Neutrality	Stability	Compatibility	Transparency
RF	$---$	$-$	$-$	$+$
GWP	0	0	0	0
EGWP	$++$	0	0	0
GTP	$-$	$-$	$-$	$+$
iGTP	$++$	0	0	$-$
ATR	$++$	0	0	$-$
GWP*	0	$---$	$---$	$---$
EGWP*	$+++$	$---$	$---$	$---$

364 whereas GWP* is better suited for linking cumulative CO₂-equivalent emissions to
 365 global mean temperature.

366 *Climate metric transparency*

367 The transparency requirement evaluates how difficult it is for non-specialists to under-
 368 stand the metric and implement it into climate frameworks. Endpoint metrics such
 369 as RF and GTP are the most straightforward to understand, while integrated climate
 370 metrics show more complex behaviour. Their calculation requires to average or inte-
 371 grate over a dedicated time horizon. Among integrated metrics, the GWP is the most
 372 simple to understand since it represents cumulative RF. The simplicity in understand-
 373 ing together with an easy calculation method and availability of data needed for its
 374 calculation are the reasons for its continuous use in climate policies and assessments.

375 Compared to metrics based on radiative forcing, temperature-based metrics (GTP,
 376 iGTP, and ATR) and EGWP are more complex to implement. These temperature-
 377 based metrics incorporate efficacy values of radiative forcing derived with global
 378 coupled ocean-atmosphere general circulation models (coupled GCMs) and hence
 379 uncertainties associated with climate modelling. These uncertainties can however be
 380 integrated in the climate impact assessment (see Sect. 5 for details).

381 The GWP* and EGWP* metrics are the least transparent and simple as they
 382 require an understanding of the relation between emissions from short-lived climate
 383 pollutants and CO₂ pulse emission. Additionally, their implementation can be compli-
 384 cated by the fact that these metrics require a temporal emission profile 20 years prior
 385 to the considered instance as well as a value of the AGWP for a CO₂ pulse that has
 386 to be calculated for each background scenario.

387 **3.3 Down-selection of climate metrics for the use in climate** 388 **impact technology assessments**

389 Table 2 summaries the performance of the climate metrics against the requirements.
 390 Performance is ranked from $---$ (very low) to $+++$ (“very high”) based on a
 391 revised version of Table 1 from [41]. In the context of technology impact assessments,
 392 the neutrality requirement is given the highest priority, as reflected in the highest
 393 ratings compared to other requirements for the metrics that perform well against

394 this criterion. The end-point metrics RF and GTP have generally low ratings, mainly
395 owing to their strong dependencies on the time horizon and temporal emission profile
396 (scenario), resulting in low neutrality and stability. Also, end-point metrics are limited
397 to a single point of time in the future (H) and hence do not preserve an indication
398 if the technology caused a rise in temperature prior to the time horizon. In contrast,
399 integrated metrics accumulate the effect of increasing temperature (or RF). Among
400 the considered metrics, the EGWP* shows "very high" neutrality, but at the same
401 time it has poor performance against the rest of the requirements and therefore is not
402 recommended. The ATR and EGWP metrics show high neutrality and the highest
403 overall ratings in Table 2, making them a good overall compromise. Note that the
404 conclusions of the selection procedure are applied for both relative and absolute metric
405 forms.

406 The ATR, as a temperature-based metric, has the potential to include more cli-
407 matic processes, aligns better with Paris agreement and thus is more relevant for
408 temperature-based policy targets than the GWP. The EGWP, by incorporating effi-
409 cacy values, allows its RF basis to more closely align with temperature-based metrics,
410 thus more accurately representing the climate impact of aviation while retaining the
411 GWP's methodological structure. Although the iGTP and the ATR differ only by a
412 factor of H , the units of the ATR are more straightforward to understand, making this
413 metric our choice.

414 As discussed in Sect. 3.1, choice of the time horizon plays an important role in
415 the assessment of climate impacts and cannot be determined based on first principle.
416 A longer value (longer than 70 years) is recommended for several reasons: 1) metrics
417 demonstrate a decreasing sensitivity with time horizon, 2) a longer timescale is nec-
418 essary to capture the full impact of long-lived gases, and 3) long horizons are more
419 appropriate for policy goals when the eventual magnitude of climate change and long-
420 term risks are the primary concerns. For consistency with existing policy, H of 100
421 years is appropriate.

422 3.4 Discussion of climate metric choice

423 The choice of a climate metric often involves subjective value judgments that can influ-
424 ence it, as discussed during the stakeholder workshops. The neutrality requirement
425 offers an objective weighting of metrics based on a quantitative estimate of how effec-
426 tively a metric represents a chosen physical indicator. This requirement was therefore
427 deemed to be the most important at the stakeholder workshop. Moreover, stakeholders
428 proposed that the neutrality requirement could be renamed to "being representative
429 of temperature change". However, we stress that the evaluation procedure can be also
430 applied with another physical indicator representing climate change such as RF. The
431 choice of physical indicator for metric evaluation should align with existing policies.

432 Fuglestedt et al. [53] noted that the problem with identifying an alternative to
433 the GWP metrics is "the lack of a well-pronounced goal for combating climate change
434 that a metric is to serve". In 2015, the Paris Agreement specified limiting the global
435 average surface temperature raise to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels as such a goal.
436 This makes temperature-based metrics more relevant for climate policies. Since the
437 Paris Agreement does not specify the year when this goal has to be met, its goal can be

438 interpreted as limiting the peak temperature. In this context, the peak temperature is
439 a preferable physical indicator over radiative forcing. Note that a climate assessment
440 of any technology assuming a limited technology life time yields a peak in temperature
441 response.

442 In contrast to the peak temperature, selecting a temperature change measured at
443 a certain time horizon as an alternative climate indicator introduces a potential issue
444 that the sign of the temperature change could reverse, depending on future emission
445 scenarios. Therefore, the GTP metric, which was proposed and extensively discussed in
446 the literature as an alternative to the commonly used GWP, under-performs w.r.t. the
447 neutrality requirement in comparison to integrated temperature-based metrics such
448 as the ATR. As expected, the GTP metric, similar to the other end-point metric RF,
449 indicates a higher frequency of the incorrectly identified fleet pairs (lower neutrality)
450 and is less representative of the peak and average temperature changes.

451 The other requirement with a quantitative approach is metric stability over time.
452 It was ranked second in importance at the stakeholder workshop, which underscored
453 that metrics should be insensitive to small changes in the time horizon. Nonetheless,
454 this criterion is broader and also ensures accurate and consistent assessments over
455 different time periods, a point that, as Megill et al. [41] argue, is relevant for policy
456 monitoring.

457 As mentioned in Sect. 3.2, the temperature-based metrics introduce additional
458 uncertainties in the climate impact assessment through uncertainties in modelling of
459 efficacies of aviation climate forcings. However, these uncertainties can be integrated in
460 the climate impact assessment, together with other uncertainties discussed in Sect. 5.
461 The primary advantage of these metrics lies in their clearer alignment with the objec-
462 tives of the Paris Agreement, which significantly strengthens their applicability. The
463 feedback received in the stakeholder workshop corroborates the importance of this
464 argument.

465 **4 Resulting best practice for a technology climate** 466 **impact assessment**

467 In the following, we combine the results from the literature study on technology impact
468 assessments (Sec. 2.4) with the findings from selection of climate metrics presented
469 in Sec. 3 to derive a best practice for a technology impact assessment (Sec. 4.1) and
470 provide an example in Sec. 4.2.

471 **4.1 Description of four-layer approach**

472 In this section, we suggest the following four-layer approach as a best practice for a
473 technology climate impact assessment (Fig. 3). A new technology may encompass an
474 entire aircraft or a component, such as a new engine. In the first layer, we consider
475 in detail where this technology is used by specifying the network. This is combined
476 with an expected entry-into-service and temporal evolution (see Sect. 2.4 for various
477 scenarios of temporal evolution). Note that there might also be a relationship between
478 the entry into service and the network. This forms the basis for a detailed calculation
479 of a 3D or 4D emission inventory (second layer). Using these emission inventories,

Fig. 3 Sketch of the four-layer approach for the technology climate impact assessment (green part, see Sec. 4.1 for details) and the consideration of consequences from gaps and uncertainties in the assessment approach (blue part, see Sec. 4.3 for details)

480 the non-CO₂ impacts can be assessed with an appropriate model (third layer). Here
 481 a more detailed atmospheric model that considers the sensitivity of non-CO₂ effects
 482 with respect to geographical location and altitude is used to calculate the temporal
 483 evolution of the radiative forcing and temperature changes. Finally, these time series
 484 are used to calculate the climate metrics ATR100 and EGWP100 (Sec. 3.3).

485 It is important to note that although the end result of the climate impact assess-
 486 ment is a single value of the climate metric, the understanding of how this value is
 487 derived is key in the application of this procedure. This requires a detailed diagnos-
 488 tics parallel to the four-layer approach that enables a deeper understanding of the
 489 assessment of the individual steps. Those are for example total emissions and emission
 490 indices for the second layer, atmospheric composition changes, contrail flight kilome-
 491 ters, and time series of RF and temperature changes in the third step, and some
 492 alternative metrics in the last step.

493 4.2 Use Cases based on AS4D

494 In the following, we discuss use cases where the four-layer assessment proposed in
 495 the preceding section was applied to evaluate specific aircraft designs expected to
 496 enter service in the mid-2030s. The evaluation was performed using the ATR100 and
 497 EGWP100 metrics recommended in Sect. 3. We employ the AirClim Surrogate Model
 498 for Design (AS4D) that incorporates the four-layer approach to quantify the climate
 499 response of potential aircraft concepts at the preliminary design stage (see Appendix A

Fig. 4 Climate impact in the SMR use case: (a) Normalized CO₂-eq values vs. 2020 baseline under conventional and SAF scenarios for both state-of-the-art and 2035 concept aircraft, evaluated using ATR100 and EGWP100. (b) Total and individual climate agent mitigation potentials illustrating sensitivity to climate metric choice.

500 for description and verification). AS4D benchmarks various technological configura-
 501 tions relative to one another, rather than to deliver absolute climate impact values.
 502 The present study assess the impact of specific aircraft designs expected to enter into
 503 service around 2035 compared to 2020 state-of-the-art technology (baseline).

504 The use cases were selected from the regional and short- to medium-range mar-
 505 ket segments, reflecting current research and innovation priorities, and for which
 506 AS4D provides dedicated modeling capabilities. For comparative purposes, baseline
 507 aircraft were identified to represent each market segment: the regional segment was
 508 characterized by a reference design similar with the top-level aircraft requirements
 509 and performance characteristics of the ATR72-600, while the short- to medium-range
 510 segment was represented by a configuration similar to the A321neo [54].

511 While the baselines provide a reference for current technology, future aircraft con-
 512 cepts were modeled through fully iterated design studies to capture the potential
 513 performance and climate benefits of advanced configurations. For the regional mar-
 514 ket, a plug-in hybrid-electric configuration was selected, operating fully electric for
 515 missions up to 300 NM, followed by hybrid-electric propulsion using a kerosene or SAF-
 516 powered gas turbine [55]. The concept for this use case and segment is referred to as
 517 the Hybrid-Electric Regional 2035 (HER-2035) aircraft. For the short-medium range

Fig. 5 Climate impact in the HER use case: (a) Normalized CO₂-eq values vs. 2020 baseline under conventional and SAF scenarios for both state-of-the-art and 2035 concept aircraft, evaluated using ATR100 and EGWP100. (b) Total and individual climate agent mitigation potentials illustrating sensitivity to climate metric choice.

518 segment, a conventional configuration with a high-aspect-ratio wing was chosen, also
 519 powered by kerosene or SAF, and incorporating an ultra-high bypass ratio turbofan
 520 engine, along with advanced structural components and aircraft systems (SMR-2035)
 521 [56]. After future concepts and baseline technologies were defined, emission inventories
 522 and respective climate responses were calculated using AS4D for temporal evolution
 523 of emissions described in App. A.1.

524 The resulting performance and climate impact metrics are presented in Figs. 4 and
 525 5 and include two distinct fuel scenarios: one with conventional fuel and one with SAF,
 526 assuming an 80% reduction in soot emissions and 80 % CO₂ life-cycle savings through
 527 the use of CO₂-neutral fuel. To facilitate a clearer interpretation of the results and
 528 the implications of climate metric choice for aircraft operating across different market
 529 segments and networks while incorporating advanced technologies, the outcomes have
 530 been categorized into two main components for each segment. Accordingly, Figures 4a
 531 and 5a compare normalized CO₂-eq values against the 2020 baseline, while Fig. 4b
 532 and 5b illustrate the total mitigation potential as well as the isolated mitigation of the
 533 individual climate agents (CO₂, H₂O, NO_x, and contrails), thereby enabling a direct
 534 comparison of technology scenarios and their sensitivity to the chosen climate metric.

535 In particular, for the short- to medium-range segment, comparison across the pro-
536 posed climate metrics reveals that EGWP100 attributes a lower relative contribution
537 of non-CO₂ effects to the total climate impact than ATR100. This trend is evident
538 for both the SMR-Baseline and SMR-2035, although the differences remain small
539 (Fig. 4a). Apart from this difference in magnitude, the relative contributions of the
540 individual climate metrics appear largely consistent with one another. For the regional
541 segment, a similar trend is visible, with overall CO₂-eq values being lower than in the
542 SMR segment (Fig. 5a), primarily attributable to the operational characteristics of
543 these aircraft, such as operating at lower flight levels. Especially, the integration of
544 advanced technologies leads to further reductions in CO₂-eq values for both metrics.
545 The hybrid-electric configuration shows a pronounced mitigation of climate impact,
546 as battery-electric operation on missions up to 300 NM covers a substantial share of
547 the operational spectrum and thereby significantly reduces in-flight emissions. For the
548 SMR-2035, by contrast, the use of SAF, providing benefits in terms of soot emissions
549 and CO₂ life-cycle reductions, has a more pronounced effect compared to HER-2035.
550 This is partly because the HER-2035 already achieves substantial reductions through
551 its advanced propulsion system, whereas the SMR-2035 exhibits comparatively greater
552 additional mitigation potential from SAF use. This is attributable to its operational
553 characteristics, which make non-CO₂ effects, particularly contrail contributions, more
554 prominent for the SMR case.

555 To further investigate the implications of climate metric choice on the assessment
556 of advanced technologies and fuel options, the analysis compares now total climate
557 impact reductions and individual contributor effects relative to the state-of-the-art
558 baseline for both short-/medium-range and regional segments. This comparison pro-
559 vides insight into how the evaluated mitigation potential may differ, depending on the
560 selected metric under identical scenario assumptions depending on the selected met-
561 ric. For the SMR use case, Figure 4b presents the results for the SMR-2035 technology
562 scenarios. To better understand the total climate impact reductions of the use cases,
563 the analysis first examines the isolated effects of individual contributors, providing a
564 clearer basis for interpreting the total mitigation potential. For the SMR-2035 with
565 conventional fuel, the comparatively higher climate impact from H₂O and contrails is
566 mainly attributable to its higher cruise altitudes and improved propulsive efficiency,
567 both of which increase the likelihood of forming thicker and more persistent contrails.
568 Under the SAF scenario, H₂O-related impacts increase further due to the specific fuel
569 properties of SAF, while contrail impacts decrease as a result of reduced soot emis-
570 sions. Additionally, life-cycle savings from the use of CO₂-neutral fuel further reduce
571 overall CO₂ emissions, and thereby the associated CO₂-related climate impact. It is
572 worth noting that, in the current setup, AS4D uses wingspan as a proxy for aircraft
573 mass, and thus for vortex generation and descent speed. Larger wingspans typically
574 produce stronger vortices that descend more rapidly into warmer layers, thereby reduc-
575 ing the likelihood of persistent contrail formation. In the case of the aircraft studied
576 here, however, the high-aspect-ratio wing would generate weaker vortices that descend
577 more slowly, potentially leading to isolated vorticed induced contrail effects similar to
578 or even greater than those of the baseline.

579 Apart from this, the effect of technology and performance characteristics differ
580 across the individual contributors. However, the choice of climate metric does not affect
581 these isolated effects, as they only reflect changes within each contributor and, in this
582 case, depend solely on the selected scenario. For the total climate impact, the choice of
583 metric can in principle have an effect, as it may weight the contributions of individual
584 climate agents differently. In the present analysis, however, the results indicate that
585 the overall climate impact is very similar for both ATR100 and EGWP100. In partic-
586 ular, for the SMR-2035 (conventional fuel) a reduction of about 17% is observed for
587 both metrics, while for the SAF use case higher mitigation potentials of around 55%
588 are achieved, again accounting additionally for CO₂ life-cycle savings. The consistent
589 mitigation results across both metrics indicate that their underlying weightings are
590 comparable, leading to similar trends when benchmarking different technology options
591 without favoring specific technologies in the SMR market segment. For the HER use
592 case, very similar trends are observed (Fig. 5b). As with SMR, the isolated mitigation
593 potentials of individual contributors depend only on the scenario and not on the choice
594 of climate metric. The relatively high reductions in CO₂, H₂O, and NO_x compared
595 to the SMR case can be primarily attributed to lower fleet-level fuel burn enabled by
596 the fully- and hybrid-electric operations of the HER-2035, as concluded previously. In
597 particular, for the HER-2035 with conventional fuel, a total mitigation potential of
598 around 76% is achieved, while with SAF this increases to about 88%. Again, both met-
599 rics show similar trends and robustness, confirming that the ATR100 and EGWP100
600 metrics, recommended in Sect. 3 do not bias the benchmarking of technologies.

601 To conclude, across all scenarios a comparable total climate impact reduction
602 is observed, with variations remaining below 1%. Consequently, both climate met-
603 rics demonstrate very similar overall trends. When interpreting the presented overall
604 mitigation potentials, however, it should be noted that this use case represents an aca-
605 demic exercise, with outcomes highly dependent on the specific study setup, including
606 the choice of reference and baseline aircraft, engine type, forecast scenario, network
607 configuration, and operational assumptions.

608 4.3 Discussion of the best practice

609 The example in Sec. 4.2 nicely shows the applicability of the 4-layer approach, pre-
610 sented in Sec. 4 even at the stage of a pre-design. Although the results are eventually
611 summarised in two climate metrics, the additional diagnostics, such as the contribu-
612 tion of individual emissions to the climate metric value, allows for a deeper analysis
613 of the results. The 4-layer approach relies on the experience from earlier work, such
614 as Terekhov et al. [57], Linke et al. [11] and Grewe et al. [24] for the individual steps
615 from the aircraft type to the emission inventory and combines those with ideas on the
616 integration of uncertainties in the assessment [e.g. 52]. Even if the 4-layer approach is
617 demanding, since it requires the calculation of networks, emission inventories and cli-
618 mate impact, the example shows the feasibility, moreover the integration of climate
619 impact assessment in a multidisciplinary design process is assured (Fig. A3).

620 5 Uncertainties

621 The principles of the four-layer approach that we proposed in Section 4 have been
622 already applied in the literature (see Sec. 2). However, there are still uncertainties and
623 knowledge gaps and their impacts require better understanding. They refer to both
624 the associated science and the approach itself. In Sec. 5.1, we briefly discuss them and,
625 in Sec. 5.2, propose addressing these uncertainties in the four-layer approach.

626 5.1 Description of uncertainties

627 *Atmospheric science*

628 Assessments of the current knowledge in climate science [58] and especially aviation
629 related atmospheric science [1, 7, 42, 59] nicely present the state-of-art in aviation
630 related science that is evaluated in terms of the level of scientific understanding
631 (LOSU) that comprises both the theoretical knowledge and the amount of data avail-
632 able. Along the process chain from emissions to atmospheric composition changes,
633 radiation budget to climate metrics, all processes are described in approximations that
634 include uncertainties. A detailed description and assessment are beyond the scope of
635 this paper and we limit ourselves to a more general description.

636 The calculation of emissions is based on assumptions of the aircraft trajectory,
637 thrust settings and fuel composition, which are accompanied by uncertainties. The
638 emitted species experience transformation in the plume and are further advected with
639 the general circulation and again experience chemical and micro-physical transfor-
640 mation processes, which also affect other species, before they are removed from the
641 atmosphere, i.e. by dry deposition at the Earth's surface or wet deposition by rain.
642 For example, contrail plume processes are important since they influence the char-
643 acteristics of a contrail like ice crystal number densities and thereby its lifetime and
644 radiative effects [e.g. 60, 61]. The plume processes also affect the soot and sulphate
645 processing that eventually may affect natural cloud processes [e.g. 62, 63] and the NO_y
646 partitioning [e.g. 64, 65].

647 The atmospheric background conditions in form of chemical composition including
648 greenhouse gases, aerosols and cloudiness are important not only since they impact
649 those transformation processes, but also because they impact radiative processes and
650 especially calculation of radiative forcing. The changes in atmospheric composition
651 and radiation eventually lead to temperature changes that can be described by the
652 climate sensitivity parameter. The changes in composition, radiation temperature also
653 trigger feedback processes. The concept of the effective radiative forcing includes fast
654 feedbacks, also called adjustments, such as changes in natural clouds due to the con-
655 trail induced water budget changes [66, 67] and slow feedbacks via changes in ocean
656 temperatures [68]. The level of the scientific understanding is very different from pro-
657 cess to process. For example, the conditions when a contrail forms are well established
658 and there is a wealth of data from measurements and modeling available, whereas the
659 impact of aerosol emissions on natural clouds is highly uncertain. Data for efficacies
660 are sparse especially for aviation related effects.

661 To cover all these uncertainties in an assessment is extremely difficult and either
662 multi-model estimates or expert judgements are often used [1]. Dahlmann et al. [52]

663 and Grewe et al. [3] used more aggregated estimates of uncertainties covering the
664 entire chain from emissions to temperature changes by introducing uncertainties in the
665 atmospheric lifetime of a composition change, an uncertainty in the radiative effect
666 and an uncertainty in the temperature effect.

667 *Assessment methodology*

668 In addition to the uncertainties described above, the four-layer method (Sec. 4) also
669 include uncertainties. In the first layer both the network and the temporal evolution
670 of the technology usage (e.g. EIS) include various uncertainties. These uncertainties
671 are associated with such questions as:

- 672 • how many city pairs are required to obtain a robust result?
- 673 • how sensitive is the assessment to changes in the network?
- 674 • how sensitive is the assessment to the choice of the EIS?

675 Furthermore, the temporal evolution affects the assessment. Although the choice
676 between a life-cycle emission evolution (L) and an evolution similar to a future sce-
677 nario (F) (see Sec.2 for details) may have only a small impact on the assessment, a
678 quantification has not yet been done. Regarding the second and third layers, which
679 include calculations of the 3D emission inventory and of RF and temperature change
680 (dT) time series, all uncertainties discussed in the previous paragraph apply. In the
681 fourth layer, selection of the climate metric is obviously limited (Sec. 3), but still some
682 choices can be made concerning, e.g. the details of the temporal development of emis-
683 sions and time horizon. The sensitivity of the assessment outcome to the choice of
684 the climate metric is likely not essential as we have already limited the number of cli-
685 mate metrics [9, 33, 50]. However a good understanding of all the assumptions of the
686 assessment is lacking.

687 **5.2 Best practice in dealing with uncertainties and knowledge** 688 **gaps**

689 The previous section clearly indicated a need to integrate gaps and uncertainties into
690 the technology climate impact assessment. We identify four main areas that we discuss
691 briefly in the following and that are indicated in blue in Fig. 3.

692 *Understanding of the most sensitive parameters*

693 As a first step, we recommend establishing a good understanding of the impact of
694 uncertainties in all of the four steps of the approach on the final outcome. Identifying
695 the most sensitive parameters is key in understanding the robustness of the methodol-
696 ogy. Note that for different technologies, such as long-range and regional or SAF-driven
697 and hydrogen-driven aircraft, the sensitivities might change. Nevertheless a general
698 overview would help in prioritising future research activities.

699 ***Developing robustness metrics***

700 As described above the uncertainties from both atmospheric science and the four-layer
701 approach itself (Sec. 5.1) will translate into uncertainties in the climate impact assess-
702 ment of a specific technology. This can be addressed by defining probability density
703 functions to each parameter of the four-layer approach and perform a Monte-Carlo
704 simulation to allow the understanding of the propagation of uncertainties. Dahlmann
705 et al. [52] give a respective example for such an approach and stressed the impor-
706 tance of analysing the difference in technologies within the Monte-Carlo simulation to
707 take advantage of possible correlations of uncertainties that equally apply to either
708 technology. They found that the uncertainty ranges of relative differences between
709 technologies are the most effective robustness metrics.

710 ***Updating towards new consolidated research findings***

711 As described above, the processes that are included in the four-layer approach are
712 associated with uncertainties that can be characterised. In contrast, knowledge gaps,
713 such as the indirect cloud effects, refer to processes where the understanding is not
714 mature enough to be integrated in the four-layer approach. Here it is necessary to
715 allow updates to the assessment approach, whenever consolidated research leads to a
716 sufficient maturity level. ESTEC [69] has proposed a grading for a scientific readiness
717 level (SRL), though for the maturity of evolving science with respect to a mission
718 concept, satellite mission, or satellite instrument activity. However, as a concept it
719 might help to develop a similar SRL for deciding when a process should be integrated
720 in the technology climate impact assessment.

721 ***Verifying the assessment procedure***

722 The four-layer approach integrates complex interdisciplinary processes from aeronau-
723 tical engineering to climate science. As for any model, the proof of applicability is
724 necessary. While for the individual layers individual processes can be validated against
725 observational data, there is no possibility to validate the entire approach against obser-
726 vational data. However, a verification with higher fidelity models, for example using
727 a modelling chain from LES models to climate-chemistry models ([23]), for selected
728 independent use cases is mandatory.

729 **6 Summary and Conclusion**

730 We present an overview on methods that were applied in aviation climate impact
731 assessments and summarise requirements for climate metrics. Based on this litera-
732 ture review, we derive a best practice for technology climate impact assessment that
733 comprises 4 layers: (1) temporal and spatial technology use; (2) three-dimensional
734 aircraft trajectory and emission inventories; (3) time series of radiative forcing and
735 induced near-surface temperature changes; and (4) the climate metrics ATR100 and
736 EGWP100. The four layers are necessary to obtain a ratio between non-CO₂ and CO₂
737 effects that is in line with the respective scenario assessment and considers the spatial
738 sensitivity of the non-CO₂ effects.

739 For further steps, it is important (1) to improve the understanding of the most
740 sensitive parameters in this approach; (2) to test the approach of including uncer-
741 tainties that stem from both the method itself and atmospheric science in order to
742 obtain robust estimates; (3) to provide a verification on the basis of higher fidelity
743 models; and (4) to provide a consolidated framework for incorporating new findings
744 into (atmospheric) research depending on the level of scientific understanding or the
745 scientific readiness level.

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759 of the manuscript was written by VG, SZ and PB. Two workshops were held to
760 obtain stakeholder feedback that was included here. All authors contributed to the
761 preparation and execution of the workshops. PB and PR prepared the results for the
762 use cases with AS4D. VG, MN, BL, KD, FL and SM developed the AS4D model.

763 **Appendix A AirClim Surrogate Model for Design -** 764 **AS4D**

765 The AirClim Surrogate Model for Aircraft Design (AS4D) enables assessment of an
766 aircraft’s potential climate impact at the pre-design stage by integrating non-CO₂
767 effects into the multidisciplinary design (MDO) process. The model and its underly-
768 ing pre-calculations are described in detail in Sec. A.1. Based on these simulations,
769 AS4D provides response surfaces that allow designers to rapidly evaluate fleet-level
770 climate impacts of design trajectories, as demonstrated in Sec. A.2. This approach
771 supports efficient exploration of design options and trade-offs between performance
772 metrics such as fuel consumption and climate effects. An overview of model verifica-
773 tion, demonstrating how accurately AS4D reproduces AirClim results, is provided in
774 Sec. A.3.

Fig. A1 Surrogate modeling approach of AS4D: bypassing high-resolution emission and climate simulations via fast-access response surfaces to assess the aviation climate impact of global technology rollout. For the pre-calculated data (green, left) the application of the 4-layer approach is identified (see Sec. 4.1). The user perspective is shown in yellow (middle) and input-output data are given in blue (right).

Table A1 Key Design Parameters in AS4D.

Design Parameter	Range	Variations
Market Segments [-]	REG; SA; TA	3×
Initial Cruise Altitude [ft]	20,000-45,000	10×
Climb Angle [deg]	2.00-8.00	5×
Improved Propulsion Efficiency [-]	1.00-1.40	5×
G*-Slope [kg(H ₂ O)/J]	0.04-0.12	9×
Total number of parameter combinations		6750

775 A.1 Model development

776 Quantifying the climate impact of aviation, particularly from non-CO₂ effects, requires
777 extensive simulation of global emission inventories and their interaction with atmo-
778 spheric processes, which are computationally intensive. To enable climate assessments
779 during early design stages, AS4D uses a surrogate modeling approach based on pre-
780 calculated GRIDLAB [11, 70] and AirClim [51, 52] simulations (Fig. A1). This allows
781 designers to bypass high-resolution modeling by using fast-access response surfaces
782 representing climate effects of a full route network (Fig. A2a), requiring only typi-
783 cal aircraft design trajectories as an input. The following section describes the AS4D
784 model structure and the setup of its pre-calculations.

785 To construct the AS4D surrogate model, an extensive set of pre-calculations was
786 performed using representative aircraft design trajectories. These simulations span a
787 five-dimensional parameter space designed to capture key drivers of aviation emissions
788 and their atmospheric impact (see Table A1). We define a set of

- 789 1. **market segments** (regional jet, single-aisle, or twin-aisle), determining the route
790 network as well as fuel and emission flows of the corresponding reference aircraft;
- 791 2. **initial cruise altitudes**, reflecting the altitude sensitivity of non-CO₂ effects such
792 as contrail formation and ozone chemistry;
- 793 3. **climb rates** to that initial cruise altitude, represented by climb angles, in combi-
794 nation with market segment to capture different engine and mission configurations;
- 795 4. improved **overall propulsion efficiencies**, defined relative to the reference
796 aircraft of the market and influencing contrail effects;
- 797 5. **mixing line slopes (G*-slopes)** in the Schmidt–Appleman criterion, affect-
798 ing the likelihood of contrail formation based on the aircraft and fuel-dependent
799 parameters (EI-H₂O, overall propulsion efficiency η and lower heating value of the
800 fuel).

801 For each setting, flight trajectories are calculated, and the resulting emission invento-
802 ries are split into three parts: climb, cruise and descent (Fig. A2b-d)

803 The choice of market segment (regional jet, single-aisle, or twin-aisle) affects the
804 underlying flight network and reference aircraft performance, resulting in differences
805 in total emission volumes and their geographic distribution. For each market segment,
806 city-pair connections and flight frequencies were extracted from current global flight
807 schedules and scaled to the year 2050 using Airbus traffic growth forecasts. This scal-
808 ing reflects the temporal evolution of air traffic demand, with annual growth rates
809 gradually declining from 2018 to 2130, consistent with the business-as-usual scenario
810 described by Grewe et al. [3]. For the introduction of new aircraft configurations and
811 technologies, an EIS in 2030 is assumed, followed by a 5-year production ramp-up
812 phase until 2035, a 10 years renewal of older aircraft until 2045 and a constant market
813 share of 75% until 2129.

814 To account for the altitude sensitivity of non-CO₂ effects (particularly contrail for-
815 mation and ozone chemistry) in cruise altitude optimization during aircraft pre-design,
816 pre-calculations were conducted across ten different average cruise levels ranging from
817 FL200 to FL450. Emissions and 3D emission inventories were calculated assuming an
818 idealized flight profile for each flight, with idealized emission flows throughout the
819 main flight phases. For single- and twin-aisle missions, cruise was simulated as contin-
820 uous climb, while regional missions assumed a constant cruise altitude. To capture the
821 influence of engine configurations (e.g., turbojet, turboprop) on climb rate and emis-
822 sion rate, pre-calculations were conducted across five different climb angles (2°-8°),
823 which affected cruise length as well as emission volumes and distribution. If a cruise
824 segment of at least five minutes was not feasible at the target altitude, the cruise
825 altitude was gradually reduced down to a minimum of FL200.

826 Each emission inventory was processed with AirClim to compute the temporal
827 evolution of radiative forcing and temperature change, yielding the Average Temper-
828 ature Response over 100 years (ATR100) as the climate metric. EGWP100 metric is

Fig. A2 Forecasted single aisle data for 2050: (a) route network, (b) emissions during climb (b), cruise (c), and descent (d).

829 calculated using conversion coefficient from [48]. During these simulations, we system-
 830 atically varied the overall propulsion efficiency and the mixing line slope (G^*) in the
 831 Schmidt–Appleman criterion to account for different contrail-related impacts and the
 832 likelihood of contrail formation.

833 In total, 6,750 parameter combinations were evaluated using GRIDLAB and
 834 AirClim to generate the response surfaces that underpin AS4D.

835 A.2 Model application

836 As visualized in Fig. A3, AS4D has been developed to be integrated into the MDO
 837 process of aircraft design. For its application, users must provide a set of design tra-
 838 jectories representing emission flows along predefined mission lengths, along with an
 839 assumption file containing key input parameters. These include the lower heating value
 840 (LHV) [MJ/kg] of the fuel, emission index of water vapor (EI_{H_2O}) [kg H_2O /kg fuel],
 841 CO_2 intensity of fuel production [kg CO_2 /kg fuel], fraction of CO_2 -neutral fuel [-],
 842 soot emission index (EI_{Soot}) [-], aircraft size [pax], and wingspan [m].

843 Each design trajectory is then analyzed and segmented into the three flight phases:
 844 climb, cruise, and descent. For each phase, changes in design parameters or input
 845 values are compared against the set of pre-calculated emission inventories (see Fig. A1).
 846 To best represent the input trajectories, an optimal linear combination of the pre-
 847 calculated data is calculated and scaled with improvement factors based on the design

Fig. A3 AS4D integration into MDO process of aircraft design

848 parameter changes. The same linear combination is used to calculate the resulting
 849 climate response.

850 To account for changes in aircraft size on contrail climate impact (f_{ACsize}), we apply
 851 the Bruder et al. [71] parameterization, which is based on the work of Unterstrasser
 852 and Görsch [72], using wingspan (b) as a proxy for aircraft size. To model the reduction
 853 in contrail climate impact due to decreased soot number emissions ($f_{\Delta pm}$), we apply
 854 the formulation established in Grewe et al. [3], which are based on simulations by
 855 Burkhardt et al. [60]. In this adaptation, the relative change in the number of emitted
 856 soot particles, Δpm , is modeled as a function of mass flow (m_f) and the soot emission
 857 index (EI_{Soot}).

$$f_{contrail}(b, EI_{soot}, m_f) = f_{ACsize}(b) \cdot f_{\Delta pm}(EI_{soot}, m_f) \quad (A1)$$

858 AS4D outputs the climate impact of a global rollout of a user-specific technology
 859 introduced in 2030. The impact is expressed as the ATR100 in millikelvin (mK), with
 860 individual contributions from CO_2 , H_2O , NO_x , and contrails. It also reports fleet
 861 emissions in kilograms for CO_2 , H_2O , and NO_x , along with operational data such as
 862 total flight and contrail distances in kilometers. The analyzed design trajectories and
 863 assumptions are also saved for verification purposes to prevent misinterpretations.

864 A.3 Model verification

865 Verification of AS4D was conducted in two steps. First, the response surfaces generated
 866 by AS4D were validated by comparing their mean deviations against results from the
 867 detailed AirClim model; the results are summarized in Table A2.

868 Second, a detailed verification was carried out for the single-aisle market segment,
 869 using a set of four representative aircraft that were characterised by different shapes of
 870 design trajectories and distinct emission compositions of H_2O , CO_2 and NO_x . For these
 871 aircraft, detailed emission inventories were calculated with GRIDLAB and evaluated

Table A2 Validation of AS4D response surfaces: mean deviation compared to AirClim.

Market Segments	CO ₂	H ₂ O	O ₃	CH ₄	CiC	CiC distance
Regional Jet	0.4%	0.5%	0.1%	1.2%	1.0%	0.01%
Single Aisle	0.3%	5.7%	1.0%	0.7%	0.1%	1.1%
Twin Aisle	0.2%	3.7%	0.7%	0.6%	0.25%	0.4%

872 with AirClim, forming a test dataset for model comparison. The same design trajec-
873 tories were then evaluated with AS4D, resulting in a systematically underestimation
874 of the climate metric value by 1.0%-2.3% as shown in Table A2.

875 Both verification steps indicate that the AS4D model sufficiently well represents
876 the behaviour of the AirClim model.

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